

HadISDH.marine Update Document

Kate Willett (MOHC), 4th May 2023

General Notes:

The HadISDH.marine.1.4.0.2022f contains all 12 months of 2022. There are no major changes (X). The change to using ICOADS3.0.2 from 2015 onwards (as opposed to ICOADS3.0.1) warrants incrementing the Y element. Although this new source presents a 20% increase in coverage (~1million extra observations) from essential climate variables (see <https://icoads.noaa.gov/>), for the surface humidity processed as part of HadISDH.marine there is actually an overall loss in coverage, particularly over the northern Pacific and a few other areas. The main gain in observations appears to be over the northeast Atlantic, where observations are already fairly dense. It is not clear why some observations are no longer passing through the processing chain. ICOADS3.0.2 uses BUFR reports and prioritises these over the older format of TAC where both exist. There should be more ship observations from ICOADS3.0.2 so the fact that fewer are making it into HadISDH.marine is being investigated.

This means that HadISDH.marine.v1.4.0.2022f deviates from HadISDH.marine.v1.3.0.2021f from 2015 onwards. This is particularly noticeable from 2020 onwards. Coverage is now so limited that users should be aware that HadISDH.marine cannot be representative of the true global average.

A second change is the formula for calculating wet bulb temperature from dewpoint temperature and marine air temperature. Errors were found when the air temperature was very high but dewpoint temperature very low, resulting in spuriously high wet bulb temperatures. The Stull (2011) formula is now used as this has a far wider range of applicability. See the [blogpost](#) for details.

This mostly affects the wet bulb temperature fields although differences are very small, and far less than 1 degree for the most part. Differences are larger over warm, dry air conditions, which are less of a problem over ocean. The calculated wet bulb temperature is used to decide whether to calculate vapour pressure with respect to ice or water and so this new formula can lead to very small changes in vapour pressure and variables that use vapour pressure in their calculation (specific humidity and relative humidity). Stull (2011) tends to give higher wet bulb temperatures overall which will result in fewer uses of the calculations with respect to ice and therefore fractionally higher vapour pressures and related values. As it is consistently used across the time period it should not impact long-term trends in anomalies.

Keep up to date with subsequent changes and analyses at <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/05/2022-ipdate-from-hadisdhmarinev1402022f.html>.

Version Number X.Y.Z.0000p/f:

1.4.0.2022f

Major Changes X:

- None

Minor Changes Y:

- Change of source dataset from 2015 onwards from ICOADS3.0.1 to ICOADS3.0.2 which although increasing the number of initial observations by ~20% actually reduces coverage in some regions (especially north Pacific).
- Change of wet bulb temperature formula to [Stull \(2011\); <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/apme/50/11/jamc-d-11-0143.1.xml>](#) - see [blogpost](https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/01/new-wetbulb-temperature-algorithm-for.html) (<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/01/new-wetbulb-temperature-algorithm-for.html>).

Bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

- Change in spatial coverage and regional average time series from 2015 onwards caused by new data source ICOADS3.0.2. (no increment applied as this is covered by increment Y)

Start Date DD.MM.YYYY: 1973-01-01

End Date DD.MM.YYYY: 2022-12-31

Hadisdh Data Format (Baseline documentation): <https://zenodo.org/record/7963175>

Reference: No change

- Willett, K. M., Dunn, R. J. H., Kennedy, J. J., and Berry, D. I. 2020: Development of the HadISDH marine humidity climate monitoring dataset. Earth System Science Data. 12, 2853-2880, doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-2853-2020.
- Freeman, E., S.D. Woodruff, S.J. Worley, S.J. Lubker, E.C. Kent, W.E. Angel, D.I. Berry, P. Brohan, R. Eastman, L. Gates, W. Gloeden, Z. Ji, J. Lawrimore, N.A. Rayner, G. Rosenhagen, and S. R. Smith, 2016: ICOADS Release 3.0: A major update to the historical marine climate record. Int. J. Climatol. (doi:10.1002/joc.4775).

Other notes: The HadISDH update/analyses blog is here:

<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/05/2022-ipdate-from-hadisdhmarinev1402022f.html>